

FINAL REPORT

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**Tuning EPC and SRI instruments
to deliver full potential**

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
BRG	Better Regulation Guideline
BRP	Building Renovation Passport
CBA	Cost-benefit Analysis
EC	European Commission
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EU	European Union
IA	Impact Assessment
MS	Member State
PO	Policy Option
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TSAF	Technical Support and Assistance Framework
TST	Technical Support Team

Executive Summary

The tunES **objective was to identify the best possible implementation of the revised EPBD** covering EPCs, BRPs and SRIs **in seven Member States**. The core goals are to overcome national problems and maximise energy efficiency gains from these instruments, while minimising administrative burdens and transaction costs for stakeholders.

tunES utilises the European Union's '[Better Regulation Guideline](#)' (BRG) which is used by the European Commission to prepare and reason legislative and regulatory proposals. The [BRG Toolbox](#) is a collection of 69 tools which has been iterated and improved over almost two decades. The guiding principles are designed to ensure evidence-based policy-making, involvement of all relevant stakeholders, and simpler, better legislation that avoids unnecessary burdens.

This LIFE project deployed the 'Impact Assessment' (IA) method in a simplified and tailored form for national-level use. The capacity building effort with seven assessments running in parallel enabled seven energy agencies - Austria (AEA), Croatia (EHIP), Greece (CRES), Hungary (EMI), Italy (ENEA), Poland (KAPE) and Slovenia (JSI) - to exchange at each step with the support of four research partners (UNICAS, DTU, LUT) lead by experienced BRG experts from EMPIRICA.

The main project outcome are **seven national impact assessment reports** provided to the national Ministries which are preparing the legislative proposals for the EPBD recast based on the analysis conducted in tunES using the BRG methodology.

Building on extensive stakeholder consultation, each report covers the national analysis of existing problems, setting objectives, and the design of three policy options. Following the definition of the baseline (i.e. the status quo of the

instruments), a qualitative assessment of significant impact areas and the quantitative analysis of effectiveness and efficiency and a multi-criteria analysis are conducted resulting in the recommendation of a preferred option. The annexes describe the data collected (survey, interviews and workshops), as well as the underlying model and core references. The reports have been co-designed and submitted to national Ministries with some reports expected to become public.

tunES developed common tools which can be deployed by other agencies or in similar context. The following tools are [publicly available](#): EPC-SRI Good Practice collection, Policy Measures and the Methodology Guidance and the cost-benefit-tool shared upon request.

This document presents:

- Main achievement and impacts
- Project overview
- Introduction into core methods deployed and results achieved as a first step for replication.

Core objectives (all achieved)

- Facilitate exchange on current experiences and support Member States to implement the TSAF for cross-border learning
- Engage key national stakeholders and collect missing data and evidence
- Prepare and develop national policy options
- Conduct analysis and impact assessment of policy measures to trigger legislative and regulatory measures
- Analyse all experiences and document good practice in comprehensive European guidance
- Offer technical advice, assistance and support to Member States on EPC and SRI instruments and BRG methodology.

Main project achievements

In summary, tunES accomplished the following achievements which are briefly introduced here and documented in more detail behind in the linked sections.

- *Application of EC Better Regulation Guidelines at national level using a common guidance and tools*
- *EPC & SRI Good Practice Collection*
- *Multi-Member State parallel policy design and impact assessment using common methods and tools*
- *Engagement of National Ministries*
- *Seven national impact assessment reports*
- *Deliverables and publications*

tunES was the first project to **deploy the Better Regulation Impact Assessment** procedure in a harmonised manner **across multiple Member States at a national level**. For all seven Energy Agencies, this process was new and a significant departure from their usual practices. Building on the BRG Toolbox, tunES successfully developed capacity-building tools to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. tunES co-developed the required

common tools and successfully deployed methods such as problem-tree analysis, surveys, stakeholder consultations, and cost-benefit and multi-criteria analyses, which were included in **the Methodology Guidance**. All energy agencies successfully **learned the methods, applied them in parallel and engaged with national Ministries** and co-developed policy options to prepare the national implementation pathway.

All efforts culminated in **seven extensive national impact assessment reports forming the basis for the legislative procedure in the national Ministries**. These reports analyse the national situation, existing problems, and the objectives for the upcoming recast. They derive a combination of measures (i.e. policy options) that are suitable for the national landscape and assess each option against a common baseline. Based on this, preferred options were identified and recommended to the legislator, exceeding the mandatory minimum required by the EPBD. This increased ambition correlates with more and better EPCs, BRPs and SRIs, which increase the number of renovations, and thus energy savings and the amount of renewable energy produced.

Throughout the process, energy agencies benefited from peer exchange and support provided by technical partners, which was made possible through funding received from the LIFE programme. The resulting further significant achievements include:

- Harmonised collection of core insights from already successfully or currently tested practices on EPC and SRI from 83 EU and national practices in the **publicly available good practice collection**,
- **Academic publications** in *Proceedings of the 55th International HVAC&R*, *Proceedings of 10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech)*, *Energy and Buildings*, and *Proceedings of REHVA*

HVAC World Congress and **submissions under review** on the role of EPC and SRI in renovations and results of survey and interviews with stakeholders.

Main impact in influencing national policy

The seven Energy Agencies prepared Policy Options of three levels of ambition to address the objectives in their national context. The results of the Impact Assessment showed that **in six cases the Policy Option with a high or the highest ambition level should be preferred**. In other words, the reports conclude that implementation of measures beyond a minimal adaptation of EPBD results in the best balance of costs and benefits in relation to local conditions and strategic priorities. Across the seven Member States, **91% of all possible measures are expected to be implemented**, which is an increase of 58% on the 33% of measures already in place in the current baseline. Therefore, even in Member States where the highest ambition was not selected, **most measures are expected to be implemented**. An increase to 91% far exceeds the mandatory minimum, which amounts to about 66% of policy measures in the EPBD.

By implementing the evidence-driven BRG methodology, **energy agencies have achieved three major shifts in the usual approach to transposing EU legislation**, all of which have been well received by national Ministries and stakeholders.

- Energy Agencies became **proactive players** in shaping national EPBD legislation, rather than reacting to ministry requests.
- Energy Agencies documented that implementing more than the mandatory minimum is a preferable outcome, most likely **increasing the ambition of future**

legislation, through close exchange with the Ministries.

- Through deep and extended **stakeholder consultation**, Energy Agencies involved stakeholders early in the 'change process', thereby increasing the probability that the preferred options would be accepted and implemented successfully.

Recommendations

→ The European Union should consider anticipating and funding more projects in advance of expected recasts with explicit reference to the BRG methodology. An alternative are dedicated support contracts with cascading elements or commitment by Member States to provide resources to the delegated Agencies. The proactive engagement of National Authorities during the design phase significantly enhances feasibility.

→ Member States should consider whether early policy design stages must be triggered by responsible Ministries (which could be occupied by a crisis) or whether delegated agencies could not begin the process following an agreed process such as suggested by and well documented in BRG leading to interaction as demonstrated in tunES. The selected preferred options indicate an almost complete EPBD recast transposition far beyond a limitation to mandatory measures only.

→ The European Commission should consider assessing any possible difference between tunES Member States and other Member States as part of an EPBD evaluation taking into consideration that tunES shared various tools with all Member States during the process.

Value proposition to Member State ministries and their energy agencies

tunES has demonstrated that the Better Regulation approach can be utilised at a national level for policy design and impact assessment. This has led to the development of nationally tailored legislative proposals that address national challenges and provide convincing evidence for ambitious action.

The process was welcomed by stakeholders, agencies and ministries in all seven member states. Early involvement and the opportunity to contribute induces acceptance, which is reinforced by clear and transparent communication of the available evidence.

Energy agencies have proven their ability to initiate and moderate a policy design process within the context of transposition activities. The process relied on regular meetings and mutual understanding that the finalised report would be passed on to the Ministry. The purpose of the process and the resulting report is to provide the best possible basis for making good decisions.

tunES offers all the necessary tools for replication and has developed training materials that are suitable for the national context.

1 Introduction

The project evolved in context of the expected recast of the EPBD. Seven Energy Agencies decided to attempt a different approach in applying Better Regulation Guidelines on national level and proactively provide the national Ministry with an analysis of best action; rather than electing to wait until the national Ministry has specific and limited requests for information. The project builds on empirica's experience in applying BRG for the European Commission and the technical expertise of scientific experts supporting the national Energy Agencies in their analysis.

The report provides an overview of the tunES project highlighting its key insights and overall approach and introducing the methodological base. tunES was designed as a coordinated effort to support EU Member States in strengthening and aligning Energy Performance Certificates (EPC), Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), and related policy instruments through a structured, transparent, and replicable methodological framework that ensures consistency across countries while remaining adaptable to national contexts. This approach enabled the development of evidence-based policy recommendations and supported their practical implementation in diverse regulatory environments. Central to this was the Technical Support and Assistance Framework (TSAF), which builds on the EC's Better Regulation Toolbox and implements key principles such as evidence-based analysis, stakeholder engagement, and impact assessment throughout the process. By applying this common framework, tunES ensured coherence and alignment with EU standards for legislative preparation, also facilitating the development of integrated policy solutions to address interdependencies between the instruments.

2 tunES methods

The tunES project was built on a structured and replicable methodological framework designed to support Member States in improving and integrating EPC, SRI, and related instruments. tunES deployed a Technical Support and Assistance Framework based on the European Commission's Better Regulation Toolbox. This ensured that all policy development activities followed a coherent, evidence-based, and impact-oriented approach aligned with EU standards for legislative preparation.

Initially, the project addressed five building blocks (Understanding EPC, Upgrading EPC, Databases and Tools, SRI Development and Deployment, and Integration of Instruments) in parallel which was later mapped against the recast structure of the EPBD. This helped to identify overlaps and dependencies across instruments and avoid fragmented policy development. The Technical Support Team prepared common methods (e.g. survey, interview guides, policy design, and impact assessment tools), which were tested, refined and applied by Energy Agencies. Figure 1 illustrates the process of collaborative shaping of policy from data collection to implementation.

Figure 1. Methodology overview

The methodological steps started with structured desk research and analysis of good practices, reviewing EU legislation (drafts and later the EPBD recast), national frameworks, and results from relevant LIFE and Horizon projects (see [“Desk research: Good practice collection to find alternatives to current state”](#)). To complement the research, tunES deployed primary data collection tools, including multilingual online survey, structured interview guides, and national stakeholder workshops. Interviews with National Authorities established clear reference points regarding political priorities, regulatory constraints, and strategic objectives (see [“Analysis of status quo: stakeholder consultation”](#)).

Policy design process followed structured multi-step BRG approach. Each Energy Agency first developed a problem tree identifying drivers of the problem, followed with an objective tree to link problems to measurable policy objectives (see [“Define the problem and objectives”](#)). Based on desk research, stakeholder input and identified use cases, a range of policy options was developed. Policy options were checked for coherence across building blocks and refined with TST and bilateral consultations with National Authorities (see [“Development of Policy Options”](#)).

Impact assessment was conducted using a developed Impact Assessment Tool, integrating Cost-Benefit analysis (CBA), Multi-Criteria analysis, qualitative and quantitative indicators aligned with BRG standards (see [“Analyse the impacts with a clear methodology”](#)). The framework allowed comparison of policy options across multiple dimensions such as effectiveness, efficiency, coherence, and broader economic, environmental, and social impacts. This complex process allowed structured comparison of options and transparent identification of preferred policy packages. The process is generally reserved for EU legislation process; to our knowledge tunES was the first project attempting to deploy the BRB impact assessment method during national transposition.

2.1 Desk research: Good practice collection to find alternatives to current state

Any policy changes should consider already available good practice across Member States including those developed in recent Horizon 2020 and LIFE projects. Our **good practice collection** identified, described, and iterated already successful or currently tested practices on EPC and SRI design, deployment, and implementation.

We **collected 83 practices** with some support of the community (the editable version remains available, including through the Next Gen EPC cluster) covering 18 EU projects. Each practice is linked to at least one of the following building blocks:

- **Understanding EPC** collects practices on how the EPC itself, or linked results can be better understood by all involved stakeholders.
- **Upgrading EPC** collects practices on improving and optimising EPC methodology, generation process, or indicators.
- **Databases and Tools** collects practices on (existing or new) data infrastructure and tools requiring central or federated data management.
- **SRI Development and Deployment** collects practices implementing SRI calculation methodology and the necessary processes as well as linked use cases.
- **Integration of Instruments** collects practices that integrate EPC and SRI and/or achieve harmonisation, efficiency, and interoperability across EPC, SRI, and other tools.

The Good Practice Guidance provided a structured and policy-relevant overview of tested and emerging practices supporting the effective implementation of Energy Performance Certificates and the Smart Readiness Indicator across the EU. By organising practices around clear building blocks and linking them to the revised EPBD, the collection includes technical experience from European and national projects and provides actionable knowledge for policymakers and public authorities. As a living resource, it supported informed decision-making, reduces fragmentation, and facilitates consistency.

The practice collection promotes replication and transferability and fosters cross-country learning. Its systematic dissemination through EU networks and policy forums enhances EU added value and ensures that innovations in EPC and SRI design, data management, and instrument integration can be scaled up beyond the tunES project.

Overall, the guidance constitutes a foundation for future policy development and contributes to accelerating energy efficiency improvements, building renovation, and decarbonisation in the European building stock. If not used for the technical aspects of what the projects delivered, it is starting point to collect any required evidence or data on specific measures.

The EPC and SRI Good Practice Collection contains 83 practices from 18 EU projects and national projects. We have published the Collection and shared with more than 400 people in the NextGen EPC cluster inviting to co-edit and use it.

Find more information about the Collection of good practices see the document: [tunES D4.1 Improved Good Practice Guidance](#)

2.2 Define the problem and objectives

Policy makers are to solve existing problems rather than “just” making legislation. Thus, the root causes of the current national EPC implementation problems and the foreseeable challenges of SRI and BRP require a dedicated analysis before the measure itself can be designed.

Problem Tree

This tool visually maps out the main problem, its causes (drivers), and its consequences, following the approach outlined in Better Regulation Toolbox Tool #13. This tool helps to ensure that the scope of the problem is understood by considering potential causes and effects in the policy-making process.

The first step in a series of analytical approaches to resolve policy issues in their respective countries was for each energy agency to fill out its Problem Tree. The problem identification process followed Tool

Figure 2. Problem Tree

#13, in which agencies described the current situation and key challenges affecting EPC implementation. They also estimated the scale of these issues based on regional statistics.

The identification of the drivers was essential, as the policy measures aim to address them, which will ultimately affect the problem and its consequences. Following the BRG guidance, the agencies examined regulatory inconsistencies, technological limitations, and varying levels of stakeholder awareness, as well as external factors such as economic trends and technological advancements, which could influence the development of the problem.

Objective Tree

The Objective Tree converts the identified problems and their drivers into specific and measurable goals, in line with the principles set out in Better Regulation Toolbox Tool #15: ‘How to Set Objectives’. The objectives are derived directly from the problem analysis and are classified into general objectives (aligned with broader EU goals) and specific objectives (addressing the key drivers of the identified problems).

Figure 3. Objective Tree

The use of Tool #15 ensures that these objectives are precise, measurable, and time-bound, following the S.M.A.R.T. criteria:

- Specific - clearly defined
- Measurable – able to be quantified to measure progress
- Achievable - realistic and properly justified
- Relevant - linked directly to the Drivers identified in the Problem Tree
- Time-Bound - objectives within a specific timeframe to measure progress.

Common problems and corresponding objectives across Member States identified by Energy Agencies:

- **Low assessor competence.**
- **Poor data quality and weak validation.**
- **Low user understanding of EPCs.**
- **Gap between calculated and real performance.**
- **Generic, non-actionable recommendations.**
- **Fragmented and incomplete EPC databases.**
- **Low public awareness and engagement.**

Find more details on methodology: [tunES D4.1 Improved Good Practice Guidance – Methodology Guidance](#)

2.3 Analysis of status quo: stakeholder consultation

Whilst energy agencies are well familiar with the instruments, there may be differences in the assessment or incomplete understanding of the drivers. Therefore, BRG requires to conduct a large-scale, open consultation with affected stakeholders.

The tunES project conducted a survey and interviews across seven EU Member States from April to August 2024 to evaluate the current state of EPC and the SRI.

The **survey** was co-designed by Technical Support Team and Energy Agencies in English and translated into seven partners’ national languages. The stakeholders included business, authorities of local and national levels, various academic institutions, and professional associations. Similarly open questions for **a series of interviews** were prepared in English based on the survey. The invited interviewees included representatives of building owners and the occupants' associations, energy auditors and consultants, financial institutions, real estate agencies, and energy consultants. 303 stakeholders participated at survey and interviews.

A series of **national workshops** and meetings were organised in seven Member States on national level during the policy options design phase. Representatives of different target stakeholder groups were invited, including representatives of national ministries, market actors, researchers, energy experts, auditors, and consultants. The outcomes of these workshops provided valuable insights for refining further steps. The combination of informative presentations and interactive discussions encouraged cross-sector collaboration among policymakers, industry representatives, researchers, and professional associations. In total, 314 participants took part across all workshops.

The [detailed report is publicly available](#) and provides an analysis of the collected data, identifying challenges, opportunities, and regional differences in the implementation of these energy efficiency tools.

Find more information: [tunES D2.1 Report on Survey and Interview Results](#)

2.4 Development of policy options

Once it is clear what needs to change, policy measures can be selected and organised into bundles called policy options. Multiple policy options should be designed so that they can be assessed for their respective impacts. Ideally, the policy options are sorted in order of ambition for achieving the objectives, starting with basic, over advanced to comprehensive.

Figure 4. Policy Option design

Baseline	PO1 (Basic)	PO2 (Advanced)	PO3 (Comprehensive)
No interventions	Basic Measures -	Advanced Measures + Some Basic Measures	Comprehensive Measures + Advanced/Basic Measures
	Simplest form of intervention with minimal changes	More significant changes involving regulatory and non-regulatory measures	Extensive interventions with significant regulatory overhauls
	Less intrusive, low cost, limited resources	More comprehensive, higher costs, robust intervention	Highly ambitious, resource-intensive, coordinated actions

Given the analysis of tunES co-initiated with the release of the EPBD recast, the tunES project adopted the original approach and developed a publicly accessible [policy-measure selection tool](#) based on the changes to the EPBD. The design served multiple functions:

- Clearly identifying the baseline and thus demonstrating compliance with the EPBD recast;
- Providing the original legal text with references to existing guideline documents;
- Selection of up to five policy options with clear transparency on their differences across sections and articles.

Figure 5. Policy Option Selection tool

The reference to the specific articles and original legal text is provided in comments in the EPBD column for better understanding of a policy measure and easier reference.

From the seven Energy Agencies, three chose a Comprehensive PO, the most ambitious, as a Preferred one, another three decided for an Advanced PO, and only one Agency preferred a Basic PO (the least ambitious). This fact leads to high percentages of policy measures covered by the Preferred POs and consequently to 91% of measures to be transposed combining the baseline and Preferred Options in the seven MS.

Find more details on the results: [D3.3 Report On Ex-ante Testing and Policy Options](#)

2.5 Analyse the impacts with a clear methodology

The developed policy options need to be assessed. The final choice is to be based on the best available evidence free of biases. A common bias is that doing the ‘minimum’ required by EU directives is the cheapest option for any given Member States. Experience shows that this is not correct as some optional measures may solve existing inefficiencies.

A rigid and transparent methodology consisting of several steps is developed to analyse the key impacts of the policy options.

Theory of Change

At the basis lies the **theory of change** (BRG Tool #32) which is based on the most recent research available on how policy can influence the behaviour of stakeholders regarding building performance, in particular energy efficiency and renewable energy measures.

The policy option influences the following factors to achieve the specific objectives identified for resolving the causes identified in the Problem Tree:

- **Access to information, awareness and understanding** making EPC data accessible and available to both individual users and multipliers;
- **Accuracy of EPC:** improving the transparency and accuracy of EPC data;
- **Trust in EPC by individual building owners and multipliers:** enhancing reliability of the EPC process and data;
- **Efficiency (business and authorities):** improving the efficiency of administrative support and policymaking in energy efficiency sphere;
- **Integration of SRI:** implementation of SRI and integration with other systems and tools.

In combination these factors increase both the ability and the willingness to act. This makes the following desired actions more likely. Thus, the factors influence the behaviour of stakeholders, individual building owners, and multipliers (eligible parties, such as financial institutions, aggregators, energy suppliers, and energy services providers):

- **Deeper renovation:** building owners and multipliers are motivated for deep renovations;
- **Additional renovation:** building owners and multipliers recognise the effectiveness of additional renovations;
- **Renewable energy sources and storage:** ensured higher rate of RES installation and usage.

Cost-benefit Analysis (CBA)

The theory of change is implemented in the cost-benefit analysis tool which models the **effectiveness** (e.g. energy savings, emission reductions) and **efficiency** (i.e. costs and benefits for all stakeholders) as outlined in BRG Tool #63. The model provides data which can be used to assess to which degree each policy option achieves the foreseen objectives. Energy Agencies have been working on CBA individually with TST support. The calculations were iterated at consortium meetings during the workshops and common discussions.

The CBA is implemented as an Excel tool which consists of several interlinked sheets:

- Settings sheet contains all key input parameters, assumptions, consistency checks to ensure coherence across scenarios.
- Master sheet builds upon these inputs to calculate key variables used in subsequent analyses.
- Baseline sheet represents the reference scenario against which all policy options are compared.
- Policy Option sheets follow the same structure as the baseline but apply alternative assumptions that reflect the scope and design of each proposed policy, based on entries from the Settings sheet.
- Collection sheet compiles the key results from all scenarios, including a comprehensive CBA summary table and a set of relative indicators to support comparison and evaluation of the policy options.

Energy agencies and Ministries can request the Tool free of charge.

Qualitative Assessment

The qualitative assessment (BRG tools #30 and 36) is based on several data sources. These include stakeholder consultations, national workshops, survey, interviews, and desk research. The impact areas assessed include **economic**, **environmental**, and **social** impacts constituting:

- Efficiency of public authorities and businesses which also include administrative burden;
- Energy savings and resulting savings in cost of energy;
- Employment level;
- Health and wellbeing.

Multi-criteria Analysis

Multi-Criteria analysis is used to consider different policy options that go beyond economic measures and involve both quantitative and qualitative data structures as set out in BRG tool #62. The approach involves comparing these alternatives based on pre-defined dimensions, objectives, and criteria. Aside from **efficiency** and **effectiveness**, it considers **coherence** (i.e. how well each policy option corresponds with other related legislation) and **proportionality** assessing the extent to which each policy option is limited to what is necessary to achieve the objectives (i.e. ensuring it does not affect any stakeholder unduly). The findings of these assessments are translated into scores to enable the policy options to be compared.

Find more details on methodology see the presentation on methodology: [tunES D4.1 Improved Good Practice Guidance – Methodology Guidance](#)

2.6 National reports and Roll-out pathways

Using the BRG methodology, Energy Agencies prepared National impact assessment reports which represent the main project outcome. The reports have been co-designed and submitted to national Ministries which are preparing the legislative proposals for the EPBD recast.

The national reports cover all the methodological steps and contain:

- Problem analysis with problem tree
- Objective tree
- Design of policy options (based on available best practice)
- Description of the baseline (i.e. the status quo of the instruments)
- Qualitative assessment on significant impact areas
- Quantitative analysis of effectiveness and efficiency
- Multi-criteria analysis
- Recommendation of the preferred option
- Data collected from stakeholders through survey, interviews and workshops.

Whether a national report will be made publicly available is decided by Energy Agencies and/or responsible Ministry in each individual case. Some reports expected to become public.

Roll-out Pathways

Once the preferred policy option had been identified and described in the national reports, the Energy Agencies co-designed a roll-out pathway with respective Ministry **planning all the steps** to enact the option. They collected and described the required actions, providing estimated timings for the implementation of the policy option. This structured approach simplifies the policy-making process, providing policymakers with a practical roadmap to anticipate challenges and adjust measures when necessary. The identified common 6 phases for the Member States include:

- 1. Preparation and stakeholder engagement (2024-2025):** Assessment of the national building stock and identifying key barriers such as data quality, skills gaps, fragmented databases, and integration of EPC, BRP, and SRI. Broad stakeholder consultations (ministries, regional authorities, professionals, and users) are conducted to define feasible policy options and secure early buy-in for reforms.
- 2. Legislative drafting and consultation (2024-2026):** National ministries draft or revise energy efficiency and building laws to transpose the EPBD recast. Drafts are subject to inter-ministerial coordination and formal public consultations via online platforms and thematic workshops. Stakeholder feedback is used to refine texts and ensure coherence with EU guidance and national climate objectives.
- 3. Government and Parliamentary adoption (2025-2026):** Revised legislative drafts proceed through government approval and parliamentary debate for formal adoption. Some MS also adopt delegated or enabling acts authorising detailed technical decrees.
- 4. Technical regulations and digital infrastructure (2026-2027):** Ministries issue sub-legal acts to update EPC methodologies, introduce BRPs, and define national SRI procedures. Parallel actions focus on digitalisation, upgrading or rebuilding EPC registers linking EPC, BRP, and SRI data, with unique building identifiers, validation tools, and secure user access.
- 5. Capacity building, quality control, and market activation (2026-2027):** New certification and training schemes for EPC, BRP, SRI assessors are introduced, with mandatory re-examinations and stronger quality assurance mechanisms. Awareness campaigns, one-stop shops, and “one-visit-one-package” service pilots support market uptake. Financial incentives promote higher energy classes, adoption of smart technologies, and preparation of BRPs.
- 6. Monitoring, evaluation, and continuous improvement (2027-2050):** Countries plan long-term monitoring of the implemented measures through audits, inspections, and periodic updates of national renovation plans. Minimum energy performance requirements and methodologies will be revised every few years, ensuring alignment with the EU climate targets.

3 Results

3.1 Lessons learnt

The implementation of tunES across seven Member States provided valuable practical insights into policy design, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge transfer.

Main challenges encountered:

- *Limited policy analysis without BRG approach*
- *Reactive policy-making by Ministries with focus on minimum EPBD transposition*
- *Weak early stakeholder engagement and coordination*
- *Insufficient identification of root causes in existing EPC frameworks.*

Energy Agencies appreciated the **Impact Assessment approach and BRG methodology**. The application of the methodology has demonstrated the added value of a structured, evidence-based policy development approach. Energy Agencies highlighted that the BRG tools enabled them to deeply analyse the current situation, set specific objectives, and develop ambitious policy options thus supporting responsible Ministries. The method assisted in identifying challenges in current policies which enabled tailoring the transposition to avoid and remedy the causes of these challenges.

A key lesson relates to the **importance of methodological structuring and analytical tools**. The visual and operational tools provided by the Technical Support Team improved the clarity and usability of the BRG approach. Energy Agencies were able to organise complex information, ensure consistency across policy areas, and simplify the analytical process. Stakeholders and Ministries were open to tunES and welcomed such interactive and transparent approach.

Energy Agencies are proactively **engaging with nationally competent Ministries** in the design phase, rather than waiting for Ministries to transpose the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). The project demonstrated that early and continuous stakeholder engagement, as promoted by the BRG framework, is critical for effective policy design. Early discussions are more likely to focus on analysis of the national problems and consider options addressing the actual issues rather than be influenced by politics and/or aiming at a minimal implementation of EU legislation as a default option. Organised stakeholder consultations improved communication between Energy Agencies, Ministries, and stakeholders and contributed to firm results.

Despite the initial complexity of the BRG methodology, Energy Agencies feel empowered by the approach as it **increased capacity and confidence** in applying evidence-based and transparent policy processes. The technical assistance provided during the project was instrumental in building this capacity, demonstrating that structured BRG-based approach improves policy quality and enables national actors to engage more effectively in the transposition and implementation of EU legislation.

Specifically **with regard to the use and experience with EPC and SRI**, the following lessons were drawn from stakeholder consultations, survey, and interviews and adopted in Policy Options:

- **Lack of awareness campaigns:** Many countries (6) highlighted that EPCs suffered from limited public engagement, as they were often seen as bureaucratic with little practical value. National awareness campaigns and accessible digital tools should accompany SRI implementation to avoid similar issues.

- **Training and certification:** Many (5) stressed the importance of maintaining mandatory training and certification programmes for assessors. Variability in training quality for EPC assessors led to inconsistent outcomes, which should be avoided for SRI by ensuring robust, standardised training and periodic certification.
- **Actionable recommendations:** Some (4) pointed out that EPCs lacked building-specific, actionable recommendations. SRI assessments should provide clear, tailored recommendations linked to financial incentives to encourage users to take action based on their results.
- **Standardisation of data:** Some (3) recommended advancing the standardisation of data formats used for EPCs. For SRI, this would make data more useful for experts and easier to integrate across platforms.

3.2 Key findings from stakeholder consultations

Conducted survey, series of interviews and workshops with stakeholders across seven EU Member States provided insights on the current state of EPC and SRI, main challenges and weak points.

- **EPC understanding and standardisation:** While EPCs are widely recognised as important, concerns remain about their accuracy, user-friendliness, and quality of the underlying data. There is a need for standardisation and methodological improvements, particularly to make EPCs more understandable and valuable to end users.
- **Dynamic data and methodological improvements:** Introducing dynamic data-based and calculation-based EPCs could significantly improve the accuracy and relevance of energy performance assessments. However, adopting these advanced methods faces challenges, including technical difficulties and the need for updated regulations.
- **National databases:** There is strong support for creating comprehensive national databases that include all EPCs and the data used to develop them. These databases would enhance transparency, improve quality control, and provide valuable resources for future EPC development.
- **SRI awareness and integration:** Although SRIs are less familiar to stakeholders, they are seen as having significant potential to drive the uptake of smart technologies and improve energy efficiency. The report recommends setting a minimum SRI value for new buildings and integrating SRI calculations into existing EPC processes to simplify implementation.
- **Regional differences:** The survey revealed significant regional differences in confidence towards the current EPC methodology. Countries such as Hungary and Slovenia showed greater confidence in their EPC frameworks, while Poland and Italy identified several areas for improvement. This suggests that a better understanding of EPC processes correlates with a reduced perceived need for upgrades.
- **Leveraging best practices:** Successful practices identified in certain countries should be adopted to develop a more harmonised and effective EPC and SRI methodology across the EU. This includes adopting best practices in professional training, data management, and public communication.
- **Challenges in integration:** The integration of EPCs and SRIs presents both opportunities and challenges. While the benefits of this integration are widely recognised, concerns about methodological complexity, data privacy, and adequacy of existing infrastructure must be addressed to ensure its successful implementation.

3.3 Policy recommendations

The project showed that it is possible to apply the BRG Impact Assessment methodology on national level with multiple exchanging Member States working in parallel. This was made possible through a lead by a BRG-experienced partner, technical support and committed Agencies.

→ The European Union should consider anticipating and funding more projects in advance of expected recasts with explicit reference to the BRG methodology. An alternative are dedicated support contracts with cascading elements or commitment by Member States to provide resources to the delegated Agencies.

The proactive engagement of National Authorities during the design phase significantly enhances feasibility.

→ Member States should consider whether early policy design stages must be triggered by responsible Ministries (which could be occupied by a crisis) or whether delegated agencies could not begin the process following an agreed process such as suggested by and well documented in BRG leading to interaction as demonstrated in tunES.

The selected preferred options indicate an almost complete EPBD recast transposition far beyond a limitation to mandatory measures only.

→ The European Commission should consider assessing any possible difference between tunES Member States and other Member States as part of an EPBD evaluation taking into consideration that tunES shared various tools with all Member States during the process.

3.4 Guidance for replicators

This document serves as an introduction to the achievements and methods required to conduct an Impact Assessment. Whilst each method is useful, the full benefit is only achieved if the approach is implemented in its entirety. It is recommended to involve an experienced entity in the process as each method takes a particular viewpoint on data (e.g. search for companies involved in BRG framework contracts for the EC).

For the EPBD use case, with focus on EPC, BRP and SRI, the project provides extensive documentation and tools which are also introduced in the following section and [publicly available](#) or can be shared upon request. The partners and Energy Agencies of the project can be contacted to share experience or help kick-start the effort.

As a starting point, it is most helpful to understand the logic and concept of the problem-tree. This method can be trialled alone or in a group with the aim to track why problems and consequences emerge. Thus, policy action should be focused on the drivers of a problem and not the problem itself. Even though the output is little more than a single page, it will evolve in a highly iterative procedure. It requires participants to question biases, reconsider links and drives the need to ask and research missing data points. The outcome achieves a focus as to “what” really need solving (i.e. whether the scale justifies the effort) and where to start.

3.5 Deliverables and publications

All deliverables and publications published and under review are collected in a project on [ZENODO](#). This includes the following core results:

- [D2.1 Report on Survey and Interview Results](#)
- [D3.3 Report On Ex-ante Testing and Policy Options](#)
- [D4.1 Improved Good Practice Guidance – Practice Collection](#)
- [D4.1 Improved Good Practice Guidance - Methodology Guidance](#)

Transparency note: the seven national impact assessments reports have been shared a sensitive deliverable (D4.2 Impact Assessment Results) with the European Commission. The first literature item summarises the results for the Slovenian case (Sučić 2026).

The following publications have already been approved:

- B. Sučić, G. Matešić, G. Vogt, and T. Cholewa (2026) “Energy efficiency in buildings: EPC and SRI as enablers of future renovations,” *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 361, Art. no. 117502, doi: [10.1016/j.enbuild.2026.117502](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2026.117502).
- T. Cholewa *et al.* (2025), "Tuning Energy Performance Certificate and Smart Readiness Indicator to achieve full potential: methods used in tunES Project," *10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SpliTech)*, Bol and Split, Croatia, 2025, pp. 1-4, doi: [10.23919/SpliTech65624.2025.11091385](https://doi.org/10.23919/SpliTech65624.2025.11091385).
- L. Canale *et al.*, (2025) “Optimizing Energy Performance and Smart Readiness in EU Buildings: Insights from the tunES Project,” in *Proceedings of the 15th REHVA HVAC World Congress - CLIMA 2025*, C. Zilio, F. Busato, L. Mazzarella, and M. Noro, Eds., Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, vol. 788, Cham: Springer, doi: [10.1007/978-3-032-10546-2_154](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-10546-2_154).

4 Conclusions

tunES demonstrated that structured, evidence-based policy design approach, grounded in the Better Regulation Guidelines, can significantly enhance the quality and ambition of national transposition of EU legislation. By deploying the BRG Tools in a harmonised way across seven Member States, the project moved Energy Agencies from reactive implementers to proactive co-designers of national EPBD legislation. The used methodology enables Ministries to base decisions on transparent evidence.

A key contribution of tunES lies in operationalising BRG tools at national level in a consistent and replicable manner. The deployment of common analytical frameworks such as problem and objective trees, stakeholder consultations, cost-benefit and multi-criteria analyses enabled Ministries to base decisions on transparent, comparable, and robust evidence. This resulted in a clear shift away from minimum-compliance approaches towards more ambitious and context-specific policy packages.

The results show that, when supported by structured analysis and stakeholder engagement, Member States are willing and able to go beyond the mandatory requirements of the EPBD. The preferred policy options identified in tunES largely exceed baseline scenarios, strengthening the potential for higher renovation rates, improved EPC and SRI quality, and higher energy savings.

tunES has generated lasting institutional and methodological impacts. tunES has built lasting capacity within Energy Agencies and established a transferable Technical Support and Assistance Framework. The publicly available guidance and tools provide a pathway for replication in other Member States. The project confirms that early ministry engagement, structured methodology and harmonised analytical tools improve legislative outcomes as well as increase stakeholder acceptance and long-term policy effectiveness.

Finally, the project confirms that harmonised methodologies, when combined with flexibility for national adaptation, can successfully bridge the gap between EU-level policy objectives and national implementation realities. tunES therefore provides not only concrete policy recommendations, but also a proven process for designing future legislative measures in the field of energy efficiency and beyond.

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